

Assessment of Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State

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Abstract

The paper assessed Emotional intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State. Three objectives, research questions and corresponding hypothesis guided the study. The study employed descriptive survey research design. The population of the study consist of all senior secondary school class two (SSII) Students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance in katsina state. A sample size of three hundred and forty-six (Male = 165 and Female = 181) students were selected through systematic random sampling technique. The instrument adapted was Emotional intelligence scale (EIS). The reliability co-efficient of the instruments obtained was 0.79 using test-retest method. PPMC and t-test statistics were used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The finding of the study revealed that Emotional intelligence significantly correlates with academic achievement in physics. It was found that male students have higher Emotional intelligence than the female. It was also revealed that male students achieved more academically than that of their female students Based on the findings, it was recommended that the physical psychology and social environment of the schools should be developed, maintained and sustained.

Keyword: Emotional-intelligence, Achievement, Physics

Introduction

Many Psychologists have investigated academic performance and focused on the relationship between intelligence quotient (IQ) and academic achievement. Funharm and Feyter (2013) opined that cognitive abilities alone are not sufficient to account for individual differences in academic success or failure. Thus, this study sought to investigate the contributions of emotional intelligence to the prediction of academic performance among senior secondary school students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Kapp (2002); viewed emotional intelligence as "that part of the human spirit which motivates us to perform, which gives us energy to demonstrate behaviors such as intentionality, persistence, creativity, impulse control, social deftness, compassion, intuition and integrity". Indeed, Mayer, Salovey and Caruso (2004) posited that emotional intelligence is part of a class of intelligences comprising the social, practical, and personal intelligences. They have referred to these types of multiple intelligences as "hot intelligences". Mayer and Salovey (1995) cited in Ejomah (2014) posit that emotional intelligence is the ability to perceive emotions, to access and generate emotions so as to assist thought, to understand emotions and emotional knowledge, and to reflectively regulate emotions so as to promote emotional and intellectual growth. Emotional intelligence is emerging as a critical factor for sustaining high achievement, retention, and positive behavior as well as improving life success. Increasingly, schools and educational organizations are turning emotional intelligence seeking a systemic solution to improve outcomes, both academic and social.

Academic achievement, which is measured by the examination results, is one of the major mechanisms to measure the academic performance of students. Academic achievement in every society reflects the educational system's success in targeting and attention to individual needs (Aloka et al., 2018). Academic achievement according to Anja (2014) represents performance outcomes that indicate the extent to which an individual has accomplished specific goals that were the focus of activities in instructional contexts, specifically in school, college or university.

Orji (2014) suggested that due to the lack of proper knowledge on Physics students suffer in all spheres of life. There is a general consensus among educators that physics is an important and useful subject for development in every society. Therefore, from the grass root level, the teaching of Physics need to be effective and scientific. However, this research would provide students with psychological information about their abilities and potentialities by giving them insight on how they shall perceive their innate ability which can influence their academic performance in schools. It would also encourage teachers to cater for psychological needs of their students.

Despite school is being an academic institution where knowledge, skills, training and dispositions are exerted, however the researcher observed that most of our students in secondary schools could not be able to pay attention to their emotions by maintaining self-adjustment and handling good relationship with others. They are usually unable to recover from negative state of mind. These may occur as a result of poor learning condition, lack of parental care, teachers' attitude in schools or due to their current stage of development. Adeyemo, 2010 revealed that many students run away from this course both at the ordinary and tertiary levels. Isola (2010) opined that Physics as a subject remains one of the most difficult subjects in the school curriculum according to the Nigeria Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC). It is also apparent that the rate of enrolment in Physics tend to be the lowest compared to other sciences (Mekonnen, 2024).

Objectives of the study

The aim of the study is assessment of emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State Specifically, the objectives of the study were;

1. To determine relationship between Emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among secondary School Students in Rimi zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
2. To find out the mean difference of Emotional-intelligence in Physics learning between male and female Senior Secondary Schools Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
3. To find out the mean difference of Achievement in Physics between male and female Senior Secondary Schools students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study;

1. What is the relationship between Emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?
2. What is the mean difference of Emotional-intelligence between male and female Senior Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?
3. What is the mean difference of Achievement in Physics between male and female Senior Secondary School students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State?

Research Hypotheses

The following hypothesis were tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between Emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
2. There is no significant difference in Emotional-intelligence between male and female Senior Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.
3. There is no significant difference of mean achievement score in Physics between Male and Female Senior Secondary School students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Research Methodology

This research adopted descriptive survey research design. The choice of this design was informed by the nature of the problem under study and the fact that the design seeks to find out whether emotional intelligence influences academic performance of senior secondary school students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance.

Population of the Study

The population of the study consist of all senior secondary schools class two (SSII) Students during the 2022/2023 academic session in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance in katsina state.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The sample size of three hundred and forty-six (346) students from the target population was used. The sample size was estimated based on the recommendation given by Research Advisor (2006) table of sample size. Systematic random

sampling technique was used to arrive at the needed sample. In this method the researcher will take a fixed interval from the population out of which one respondent will be selected.

Instrumentation

The researcher Adapted Emotional intelligence scale (EIS) administered by Ejomah Dawanderhie Stephanie (2014). The scale is fifteen (20) items which were rated on 5 points Likert scales as Strongly agree (SA); Agree (A); Undecided (UD); Disagree (D); Strongly disagree (SD). The respondents were asked to respond to the items by a tick (√) against the appropriate option that reflect or show their personal opinion. Both face and content validity were ascertained to ensure that the items in the questionnaires measure what they supposed to measure. Test-retest method of reliability test was used to determine reliability coefficient of the instrument. Thus, reliability coefficient of 0.79 was obtained.

Method of Data Analysis

PPMC was used to test hypothesis one, and t-test for hypothesis 2 and 3 at 0.05 level of significance, respectively.

Presentation of Results

Null Hypothesis One (H₀₁)

There is no significant relationship between Emotional-intelligence and Achievement in Physics among secondary school students in Rimi zonal education quality assurance, Katsina State.

Table 1: Correlation Analysis between Emotional Intelligence and Achievement in Physics

Variables	N	Mean	SD	r-value	p-value	Decision
Emotional Intelligence	346	100.730	16.433			
Achievement	346	42.893	6.162	.735	.000	Significant

Analysis of the above table shows that, the r-value (r-cal) computed is .735 and p-value is .000 at .05 level of significance. Since the critical p-value of .000 is less than the alpha value of .05, the null hypothesis one is rejected while the basic assumption is upheld. This indicates that Emotional has positive relationship with achievement in Physics.

Null Hypothesis Two (H₀₂)

There is no significant difference in mean Emotional-intelligence score in Physics learning between male and female Senior Secondary School students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 2: t-test Analysis in Emotional Intelligence between Male and Female Students in Physics.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	DF	t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	165	104.970	16.404				
Female	181	92.549	13.097	344	7.764	.000	Significant

Table above shows that at 344 degrees of freedom and .05 level of significance, the t-value (t-cal) is 7.764 and the p-value is .000. The analysis indicates that the male students have a mean score of 104.970 and standard deviation of 16.404 while the female students have a mean score of 92.549 and standard deviation of 13.097. Since p-value of .000 < .05, the null hypothesis is rejected while the basic assumption is therefore maintained. This indicates that there is significant gender difference in the influence of Emotional-intelligence between male and female on achievement in Physics. Since the mean score of male students is higher than that of the female students, the Male students have more Emotional-intelligence than the female students.

Null Hypothesis Three (H₀₃)

There is no significant difference in mean achievement score in Physics between male and female Senior Secondary School Students in Rimi Zonal Education Quality Assurance, Katsina State.

Table 3: t-test Analysis of achievement in physics between Male and Female Students.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	DF	t-value	p-value	Decision
Male	165	52.256	5.232				
Female	181	48.123	4.812	344	2.964	.000	Significant

Female	181	50.467	5.493
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Table above shows that at 344 degrees of freedom and .05 level of significance, the t-value (t-cal) is 2.964 and the p-value is .000. The analysis indicates that the male students have a mean score of 52.256 and standard deviation of 5.232 while the female students have a mean score of 50.467 and standard deviation of 5.493. Since p-value of .000 < .05, the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant gender difference in students' achievement in physics is rejected while the basic assumption is retained. This implies that male and female students are significantly different in terms of their academic performance. Since the mean score of Male students is higher than that of the Female students, the Male students seem to have better achievement in Physics than the Female students.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings, it was further concluded that Emotional Intelligence significantly influences the achievement in physics among senior secondary school students in Rimi zonal Education quality assurance, Katsina State. Hence, there is significant difference in Emotional intelligence and achievement in physics with gender.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, it was further recommended that:

1. The inclusion of a focus on emotional intelligence as part of the standard secondary school curriculum could lead to a variety of positive personal, social and societal outcomes. Increasing emotional intelligence may not only facilitate the learning process and improve career choice and likelihood of success, but could also enhance the probability of better personal and social adaptation in general.
2. Inter-personal relationship should be created and maintained between Teachers and their students.
3. It recommended that the physical psychology and social environment of the schools should be developed, maintained and sustained. Social centers and recreational centers should be made functional in order to make the school environment an ideal place for effective teaching and learning.

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